

Green Culture Practices and Environmental Claim Validation in Manufacturing Companies in Anambra State

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Abstract

Green culture practices and environmental claim validation have become increasingly significant in the manufacturing sector, especially in developing economies such as Nigeria. This study examines the extent to which manufacturing companies in Anambra State adopt green culture practices, the effectiveness of environmental claim validation mechanisms and the challenges associated with their implementation. Drawing on the stakeholder theory, the study underscores the role of multiple actors, including regulatory agencies, consumers, and corporate entities, in fostering sustainable industrial practices. Empirical evidence suggests that while some firms have integrated eco-friendly production methods, renewable energy sources and waste recycling programmes, others engage in greenwashing (making misleading sustainability claims to enhance their corporate image). Regulatory gaps, inadequate enforcement mechanisms and limited access to green financing further hinder the widespread adoption of genuine sustainability initiatives. However, third-party environmental certifications, such as ISO 14001, have been identified as effective tools for validating sustainability claims and enhancing consumer trust. This paper argues that strengthening regulatory frameworks, increasing public awareness, and providing financial incentives for green innovation are essential steps toward fostering a more sustainable manufacturing sector in Anambra State. The study concludes with recommendations for industry stakeholders and policymakers. It emphasizes the need for stricter environmental audits, corporate transparency and collaborative efforts to drive sustainable industrial development.

Keywords: Environmental claim, Green culture, Green innovation, Regulatory framework, Validation

1. Introduction

The increasing global awareness of environmental sustainability has led to a growing emphasis on green culture practices across various industries. According to Panagiotopoulou et al. (2022), manufacturing as one of the most resource-intensive sectors has come under scrutiny for its environmental impact, including high levels of carbon emissions, waste production and excessive resource consumption. The call for sustainability has been reinforced by global initiatives such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which advocate for responsible consumption and production patterns. As a result, integrating sustainable practices into manufacturing processes has become important for reducing ecological footprints and fostering long-term economic and environmental benefits (Franco & Rodrigues, 2021).

Green culture refers to the collective values, beliefs and behaviours within an organization that promote environmental responsibility and sustainability (Liu & Lin, 2020). It encompasses a range of practices such as energy conservation, waste reduction, use of sustainable raw materials, and adherence to environmental regulations. Companies that integrate green culture practices aim to minimize their negative impact on the environment while enhancing operational efficiency and corporate social responsibility (CSR). This shift towards sustainability is not only a corporate responsibility but also a strategic approach to gaining a competitive advantage in the evolving global market where consumers and investors are increasingly prioritizing eco-conscious businesses (Hegab et al., 2023).

In Anambra State, the manufacturing sector is a critical contributor to economic growth. It provides employment opportunities and fostering industrial development. However, the rapid expansion of this sector has raised concerns about its environmental issues, including deforestation, pollution and resource depletion. Many manufacturing firms are adopting green culture practices in response to increasing regulatory pressures, consumer demand for eco-friendly products and the need for long-term sustainability (2025). Furthermore, the growing awareness of climate change and its adverse effects has propelled businesses to rethink their production models to align with sustainable development principles. Despite these efforts, there remains a significant challenge in ensuring the credibility of environmental claims made by these companies because some businesses engage in misleading marketing tactics to project an

environmentally responsible image without actual commitment to sustainability (Szabo & Webster, 2021).

Environmental claim validation is essential to prevent misleading practices such as greenwashing, where companies exaggerate or falsely advertise their environmental efforts. Regulatory bodies, third-party certifications, and life cycle assessments (LCAs) play a crucial role in verifying the authenticity of sustainability claims (Chkanikova & Kogg, 2018). However, gaps in enforcement, lack of standardized validation mechanisms, and limited public awareness contribute to the persistence of false environmental claims. Without proper validation systems, consumers may be misled into supporting businesses that do not genuinely contribute to sustainability. Doing so undermines efforts to promote environmental accountability.

This paper examines the extent to which manufacturing firms in Anambra State have embraced green culture practices and the effectiveness of environmental claim validation mechanisms. It explores the theoretical underpinnings of sustainability in manufacturing, the challenges associated with implementing green practices and the implications for businesses, regulators and consumers. Through this process, the study aims to provide insights into promoting transparency and sustainable industrial growth in Anambra State. It also seeks to highlight policy recommendations that can strengthen environmental governance and encourage manufacturing firms to integrate sustainable practices genuinely and transparently.

2. Theoretical framework

This study is anchored on the Stakeholder Theory the theory was proposed by Edward Freeman in 1984. The theory posits that businesses should consider the interests of all stakeholders—not just shareholders—in their decision-making processes. Stakeholders include customers, employees, suppliers, environmental groups, regulatory bodies, and the general public, all of whom are affected by corporate activities. Within the context of green culture practices and environmental claim validation, stakeholder theory emphasizes the role of businesses in addressing environmental concerns as part of their broader responsibility to society. Manufacturing firms in Anambra State must recognize that their operations impact multiple stakeholders, including communities affected by industrial pollution and consumers

who demand authentic environmental claims. Failure to adopt sustainable practices and validate environmental claims transparently can erode trust and lead to reputational damage.

Stakeholder engagement plays a critical role in ensuring that green culture practices are not just performative but are implemented with genuine commitment (Pucci et al., 2020). This can be achieved through continuous dialogue with environmental organizations, adherence to strict regulatory frameworks, and transparency in sustainability reporting. Companies that actively engage stakeholders in their sustainability journey often benefit from enhanced brand loyalty, regulatory compliance, and increased investment from socially responsible investors (Heslin & Ochoa, 2008). Equally, the theory highlights the power dynamics between various stakeholders. Government agencies and regulatory bodies wield significant influence in enforcing environmental compliance, while consumers can drive corporate change through their purchasing choices. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and activist groups also play a role in scrutinizing corporate sustainability claims and exposing instances of greenwashing (Busch, 2018). When the stakeholder theory is aligned with, manufacturing firms in Anambra State can establish a balanced approach to sustainability that benefits both their businesses and the broader society.

3. Green Culture Practices in Manufacturing Companies Manufacturing firms in Anambra State are gradually integrating green culture into their operations. Key practices include:

- **Energy efficiency:** Many companies have adopted renewable energy sources such as solar and wind power to reduce dependence on fossil fuels. Also, energy-efficient machinery and LED lighting systems are being introduced to minimize energy consumption. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA, 2021), energy efficiency improvements in industries have the potential to reduce global carbon emissions by 40% by 2040.
- **Sustainable waste management:** Proper waste management is crucial in manufacturing. Companies in Anambra State are increasingly implementing recycling programmes and reducing hazardous waste output. According to Unegbu & Yawas (2024), some firms collaborate with recycling companies to repurpose materials, thereby reducing landfill

waste and environmental pollution. A report by the World Bank (2021) highlights that effective waste management strategies can cut industrial waste by up to 60%.

- **Eco-friendly product design:** Manufacturing firms are shifting towards using biodegradable and recyclable materials in product design. For example, some textile companies in Anambra are replacing synthetic dyes with plant-based alternatives to reduce toxic chemical discharge into water bodies (Anyakora, 2022).
- **Employee training and awareness:** Many companies are investing in educating their workforce on environmental best practices. Training programmes on sustainable manufacturing processes ensure that employees understand the importance of reducing environmental impact and actively participate in green initiatives.
- **Water conservation strategies:** Some manufacturers have adopted water recycling technologies to reduce excessive water use. Water-efficient production systems help conserve local water sources, which is critical given the growing water scarcity challenges in Nigeria.
- **Sustainable supply chain management:** Companies are increasingly working with suppliers who adhere to environmentally responsible practices. By sourcing raw materials from eco-conscious suppliers, manufacturers reduce their overall environmental footprint.

Despite these advancements, challenges remain. Some companies struggle with the high initial costs of green technologies, while others face regulatory enforcement inconsistencies (Söderholm, 2020). However, research suggests that companies that successfully implement green culture practices experience long-term cost savings, improved regulatory compliance, and enhanced brand reputation (Sovacool, 2018).

4. Environmental Claim Validation

Environmental claim validation is crucial to ensuring that manufacturing companies uphold genuine sustainability commitments and do not mislead consumers through greenwashing. Effective validation mechanisms involve multiple levels of verification, including regulatory oversight, third-party certifications, corporate transparency measures and consumer advocacy (2024). This verification includes:

- **Third-Party certifications:** Certifications such as ISO 14001, LEED (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design), and Energy Star play a crucial role in independently verifying a company's environmental claims. These certifications require businesses to meet rigorous environmental standards, providing credibility to their sustainability efforts.
- **Government regulations:** Regulatory bodies such as the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) in Nigeria establish guidelines to prevent misleading environmental claims. Strict enforcement of environmental regulations ensures that manufacturing firms adhere to prescribed sustainability standards. However, challenges such as regulatory loopholes and inadequate enforcement mechanisms sometimes allow companies to evade compliance.
- **Life cycle assessment (LCA):** LCA is a comprehensive approach used to assess the environmental impact of a product or service throughout its entire life cycle—from raw material extraction to production, distribution, usage, and disposal. This scientific validation method ensures that companies accurately report the ecological footprint of their operations.
- **Consumer and NGO scrutiny:** Consumers and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) play a significant role in monitoring corporate sustainability claims. Public awareness campaigns, investigative journalism, and advocacy groups have exposed numerous cases of greenwashing. In the process, they have held companies accountable for false claims.

Despite these validation mechanisms, some manufacturing firms still engage in deceptive practices by using vague or misleading environmental claims without providing substantive proof. Terms like "eco-friendly," "green-certified," and "biodegradable" are frequently misused in marketing strategies (TM et al., 2024). To combat this, industry-wide adoption of standardized reporting frameworks such as the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) and Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB) can enhance transparency and credibility in environmental claims. Strengthening environmental claim validation in Anambra State requires a numerous stakeholder approach which involves policymakers, industry players, consumers and

independent certifying bodies. Regulatory reforms, public education and increased investment in green verification technologies are necessary steps toward ensuring that sustainability claims reflect genuine corporate commitment rather than mere marketing rhetoric.

5. Empirical Review

Literature on green culture practices and environmental claim validation provide critical insights into the extent to which manufacturing companies in different regions, including Anambra State, have adopted sustainable business operations. Several studies have examined the role of green corporate culture in achieving environmental sustainability. These studies demonstrate both its benefits and challenges. While some manufacturing firms have embraced green practices, others have engaged in greenwashing, making false or exaggerated environmental claims to improve their market positioning (Aliano, 2024). Understanding these dynamics is essential for evaluating the effectiveness of green initiatives in the industrial sector. A study by Liu et al. (2018) explored the impact of green supply chain management on environmental performance in Chinese manufacturing firms. Their findings indicate that companies that integrate sustainable practices into their supply chain experience improved environmental outcomes, including reduced carbon footprints and enhanced resource efficiency. This study aligns with similar research conducted in Nigeria, where firms adopting green culture practices have reported increased regulatory compliance and cost savings. However, challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, lack of technical expertise, and weak enforcement of environmental regulations remain significant barriers to widespread adoption.

In the Nigerian context, research by Iliemena et al. (2023) examined how green business culture influences corporate social responsibility (CSR) in the manufacturing sector. The study found that firms with a strong commitment to environmental sustainability tend to gain a competitive advantage by appealing to environmentally conscious consumers and stakeholders. However, the research also highlighted that some companies falsely market their products as environmentally friendly without substantive changes in production processes, a phenomenon known as greenwashing. This underscores the importance of effective environmental claim validation mechanisms to prevent misleading claims and ensure transparency in sustainability reporting.

Another empirical study by Osemwegie-Ero, et al. (2024) investigated the relationship between environmental regulations and corporate environmental responsibility in selected manufacturing firms in Lagos and Anambra States. Their research revealed that companies operating in states with stricter enforcement mechanisms demonstrated higher compliance levels with environmental standards compared to those in regions with lax regulatory oversight. This suggests that strong governmental oversight and third-party verification play a crucial role in promoting genuine green culture practices. Furthermore, the study found that firms that engaged in legitimate environmental practices experienced higher brand loyalty and consumer trust, reinforcing the business case for sustainability.

In terms of environmental claim validation, studies have shown that third-party certifications, such as ISO 14001 and the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) standards, enhance the credibility of sustainability claims. A study by Abban (2020) examined the effectiveness of third-party environmental certifications in Ghana's manufacturing industry. The study reveals that companies with accredited sustainability certifications tend to perform better in environmental audits and consumer trust surveys. However, the study also identified significant gaps in verification processes, with some companies finding loopholes to obtain certifications without actual compliance. This highlights the need for continuous improvement in environmental auditing and stricter validation mechanisms to ensure authenticity.

Furthermore, a recent report by the Nigerian Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) (2022) highlighted that only 40% of manufacturing firms in Anambra State adhere to established environmental regulations. The report emphasized that while some companies have integrated renewable energy sources and waste recycling programs, others continue to operate with minimal regard for environmental sustainability. The findings indicate that companies that implement verifiable green practices not only contribute to environmental conservation but also improve their financial performance through cost reduction and increased market competitiveness. Finally, empirical evidence suggests that while some manufacturing firms in Nigeria, Anambra State inclusive, have embraced sustainable business models, challenges such as regulatory gaps, weak enforcement mechanisms, and greenwashing persist (Söderholm, 2020). Strengthening environmental claim validation processes through

stricter regulatory policies, third-party audits, and increased public awareness can help mitigate these challenges and promote genuine sustainability in the manufacturing sector.

6. Challenges and opportunities in green culture practices and environmental claim validation

The implementation of green culture practices and the validation of environmental claims in manufacturing companies face several challenges, particularly in developing regions such as Anambra State. While there is increasing awareness of sustainability practices, systemic barriers and operational constraints hinder their full adoption. At the same time, opportunities exist for companies to leverage green practices for competitive advantage, cost reduction, and long-term sustainability. One of the key challenges in implementing green culture practices is the high cost of transitioning to environmentally friendly operations. Many manufacturing firms, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), struggle with the financial burden of investing in green technologies, energy-efficient machinery, and sustainable raw materials. Studies have shown that companies with limited financial resources tend to prioritize short-term profitability over long-term environmental responsibility (Ngwa et al., 2025). This challenge is compounded by inadequate access to green financing options, such as government incentives, low-interest loans, or tax relief programs, which could encourage businesses to adopt sustainable practices.

Another significant barrier is the lack of regulatory enforcement and oversight. Despite the existence of environmental laws and policies, enforcement remains weak due to institutional inefficiencies and corruption. A report by NESREA (2022) revealed that many manufacturing firms in Nigeria evade environmental compliance through bribery and political influence. Without stringent enforcement, companies may engage in greenwashing—making false or exaggerated environmental claims to improve their brand image without implementing real sustainability measures. The absence of strict penalties for violators further exacerbates this issue, reducing the credibility of environmental claims in the industry.

Moreover, a lack of technical expertise and awareness among business owners and employees presents a challenge. Many manufacturers lack the knowledge and skills required to implement green culture practices effectively. According to a study by Udodiugwu (2023), a significant proportion of manufacturing firms in Nigeria are unaware of best practices in waste

management, energy conservation, and pollution control. This knowledge gap underscores the need for industry-wide training, knowledge-sharing programs, and government-led initiatives to enhance capacity-building in sustainability management. On the other hand, there are numerous opportunities for companies to integrate green culture practices and enhance the validation of their environmental claims. One such opportunity is the growing consumer demand for eco-friendly products. Research has shown that consumers are becoming increasingly environmentally conscious and prefer brands that demonstrate genuine sustainability commitments (Abban, 2020). Through the adoption of green culture practices and obtaining credible third-party certifications such as ISO 14001, companies can differentiate themselves in the market, attract more customers, and enhance brand loyalty.

Another opportunity lies in technological advancements that support sustainable manufacturing. Innovations in renewable energy, waste recycling, and eco-friendly packaging provide cost-effective solutions for companies looking to improve their environmental performance. For instance, some Nigerian manufacturing firms have successfully reduced operational costs by adopting solar energy systems and biogas technology for production processes (Nwankwo et al., 2024). Such technological investments not only lower carbon emissions but also improve energy efficiency and overall profitability. Furthermore, corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives and partnerships with environmental organizations can enhance the credibility of environmental claims. Companies that collaborate with non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and government agencies on sustainability projects gain public trust and positive brand perception.

Finally, while the challenges in adopting green culture practices and validating environmental claims in manufacturing companies are significant, they are not insurmountable. It is necessary to address financial constraints, strengthen regulatory enforcement, improve technical knowledge, and leverage technological advancements to create an enabling environment for sustainable industrial practices. Through the undertaking of proactive steps toward genuine environmental responsibility, manufacturing firms in Anambra State will not only mitigate environmental risks but also enhance their competitiveness in the evolving global marketplace.

Conclusion

Green culture practices offer numerous benefits including reduced environmental impact, cost savings, enhanced regulatory compliance, and improved brand reputation. However, weak enforcement mechanisms and a lack of standardized environmental claim validation processes hinder the full realization of these benefits. Studies have shown that while a number of manufacturing companies have adopted green policies, the practice of greenwashing remains a significant problem. Without proper validation frameworks, consumers and regulators face difficulties in distinguishing genuine sustainability efforts from misleading claims. Manufacturing companies in Anambra State must recognize that long-term sustainability is not just an environmental obligation but also a business imperative. Firms that genuinely commit to green culture practices tend to achieve better market positioning, higher consumer trust, and greater operational efficiency. Furthermore, adherence to international environmental standards can open doors to global trade opportunities, making sustainability a strategic advantage.

Despite the challenges, there is significant potential for growth in the adoption of green practices in Anambra State. With increased regulatory oversight, financial incentives, and stakeholder collaboration, manufacturing firms can transition towards more sustainable models that benefit both the environment and their profitability. Companies that proactively implement green practices are more likely to adapt to future environmental regulations, ensuring long-term viability in an increasingly eco-conscious global market. Through the promotion of a culture of sustainability, Anambra's manufacturing sector can play a crucial role in national and regional efforts to mitigate environmental degradation and promote sustainable industrial development.

Recommendations

1. The government should enhance the enforcement of environmental laws by imposing stricter penalties for non-compliance and ensuring that regulatory agencies have the necessary resources to conduct effective oversight.
2. Manufacturing companies should be encouraged to obtain internationally recognized environmental certifications such as ISO 14001 to validate their sustainability claims and enhance credibility.

3. Financial institutions should provide low-interest loans and incentives to companies willing to invest in sustainable technologies, making green transitions more feasible for small and medium-sized enterprises.
4. Consumer education programs should be implemented to help the public differentiate between genuine sustainability efforts and greenwashing, thereby creating demand for truly eco-friendly products.
5. Manufacturing firms should collaborate with environmental organizations, research institutions, and government agencies to develop best practices for green culture adoption and claim validation.
6. Companies should allocate resources to research and development (R&D) in sustainable manufacturing practices, ensuring continuous improvement in their environmental performance.

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